

The Influence of Community Characteristics and Social Capital on the Form of Community Participation in the Management Facilities and Infrastructure of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo, Semarang

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Abstract:- The absence of clarity on the management of the Perumnas area in the transitional position of handing over between Perumnas and the city government like this is very interesting to study because this gap is an opportunity for research on how the attitude of the occupants of the Perumnas is when faced with problems like this. In this case, it is hoped that the initiative and creativity of the residents of the national housing complex will develop in order to achieve the goals of the SDGs, which are designed in a participatory manner. The diversity of community characteristics in social life has indirectly formed social capital, which in turn influences community participation in the management of national housing facilities. This study aims to examine the influence of community characteristics and social capital on the form of community participation in managing the infrastructure of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo. This study uses quantitative research methods with descriptive statistical analysis techniques, weighting and regression. Methods of data collection use questionnaires, field observations, and institutional surveys. The research object was the people of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo, who were divided based on the type of occupancy types 21, 36 and 45. The results showed that in general, community participation in occupants of type 36 was higher than community participation in occupants of types 21 and 45. This can be seen from the large amount of participation provided by the community. Most of the participation is given by residents of type 21 in the form of proposal, suggestions and energy. For occupants of type 36, the majority participation is in the form of advice, property, and labor. Meanwhile, for occupants of type 45, the majority participation is in the form of advice and property.

Keywords:- Community Characteristics, Social Capital, Community Participation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adequate housing and settlements are one of the basic needs such as education and health, whose fulfillment is guaranteed in 1945 Constitution article 28. This commitment to fulfilling these basic needs is also in line with the Global Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals 2030 (Sustainable Development Goals) or what is known as the SDGs, especially Goals 11.1, namely access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing, including the arrangement of slum areas, as well as access to basic urban services. The significant increase and growth of the population in the city of Semarang has a direct impact on efforts to provide housing according to the needs of the community. But on the other hand, the people of Semarang City need more simple types of houses that suit their abilities. The community's high demand for simple housing types is a problem for the government in order to improve the quality of people's lives. To get around these problems and to achieve the housing and settlement SDGs target, the government is making efforts to procure housing with the principle of building affordable housing. The government has made an effort to procure housing through the Perumnas (National Housing) program which is aimed at procuring housing for the lower middle class of society.

In the city of Semarang, the procurement of housing for the lower middle class has been carried out by Perumnas Region V Housing since 1974, one of which is Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo, which was built with good infrastructure and provided plots of land as supporting facilities for the realization of the construction being fully handed over to the government after the handover of the infrastructure, housing and settlement facilities and utilities to the Semarang City government. The current status of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo is still under Perumnas and has not yet been handed over to the Municipal Government of Semarang because Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo is still developing housing developments. But in matters of area management, it is no longer the responsibility of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo because it is considered that the status of Perumnas is just waiting for handover to the government.

The absence of clarity on the management of the Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo area in the transitional position of handing over between the Perumnas and the city government is very interesting to study because this gap is an opportunity for research on how the attitude of the occupants of the Perumnas is when faced with problems like this. In this case, the initiative and creativity of housing residents is expected to grow and develop into participation. Every housing community needs to work hand in hand in managing the environment independently in order to achieve the goals of the SDGs, which are designed in a participatory manner.

Management of excellent housing facilities and infrastructure certainly requires a lot of funding. The range of effort and costs that must be incurred by residents to manage their environment is of course different, depending on the type, quality, and scope of services. The diversity of the residents of Perumnas Sendangmulyo will certainly affect their participation in the management of existing infrastructure. The various characteristics of the community and the conditions of social capital that exist in Perumnas affect the form of community participation in the management of Perumnas infrastructure. The author will focus on examining the extent to which the characteristics of the community and social capital in Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo have an influence on the form of community participation in the management of infrastructure facilities at Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo. The results of the study are expected to be able to provide an overview of the influence of community characteristics, conditions of social capital and their participation in environmental management efforts at Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

A. Society participation

Participation according to Huneryear and Hecman is the mental and emotional involvement of individuals in group situations that encourage contributions to group goals and share their shared responsibilities (Irene, 2011). In the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 5 of 2007 states that participation is the active participation and involvement of the community in the development planning process. Participation is the determination of the attitude and involvement of each individual's desires in the situation and conditions of the organization, so that, in the end it encourages the individual to participate in achieving organizational goals, and take part in every shared responsibility.

Community participation is needed as input in the development process. The community will participate if involving the community in an activity will create a sense of ownership of the activity, so that the community will maintain and care for the results of the activity. Ramlan (in Khadiyanto, 2007) argues that community participation in development is very important as input in development.

In general, community participation can be seen from the form of community participation that is given in a tangible form (has a form) and also the form of community

participation that is given in an intangible form (abstract). Real forms of participation include money, property, labor, and skills, while forms of participation that are not tangible are thought participation, social participation, decision making and representative participation. According to Huraerah (2008), these forms of community participation can be in the form of:

- *Participation of Ideas*
Participation given in ajang sono, gatherings or meetings
- *Energy Participation*
Participation given in various activities for the improvement or development of villages, assistance to others, and so on.
- *Property Participation*
Participation given in various activities for the improvement or development of the village, assistance to others in the form of money and food and so on.
- *Participation Skills and Proficiency*
Awarded to encourage diverse forms of business and industry.
- *Social Participation*
Participation is given as a sign of communality.

B. Factors Affecting Community Participation

Community participation in social life cannot be separated from the various factors that influence social interaction. Many factors can affect community participation, including internal and external factors. Internal factors come from within the community itself. The individual characteristics consist of age, education level, type of work, length of time involved in activities, income level, length of stay and occupancy status (Slamet, 1994). On the other hand, Plumer (2000) also states that several factors influence the community to participate in the participation process, namely:

- *Knowledge and Expertise*
Basic knowledge possessed will affect the entire environment of the community. This makes the public understand whether or not the stages and forms of existing participation.
- *Community Work*
Usually people with a certain level of work will be able to spend more or not even spare the slightest time to participate in a particular project.
- *Level of Education and Illiteracy*
This factor is very influential on the desire and ability of the community to participate and to understand and implement existing levels and forms of participation.
- *Gender*
It is well known that some people still think that this factor can influence people's desire and ability to participate

in the *opinion* that men and women will have different perceptions and views on an issue.

- *Belief in a particular culture*

Communities with a high degree of heterogeneity, especially in terms of religion and culture, will determine the participation strategy used and the methodology used. Often held beliefs can conflict with existing concepts.

In addition, the factors related to participation according to Gibson and Becker (2000) are as follows:

- Population Factor (age, number of families, place of origin or place of birth)
- Socio Economic Factors (level of education, work, income, status)
- Cultural Factors (cultural norms prevailing in society)

C. *Social Capital*

Etimologically social capital (social capital) has the meaning of capital owned by the community in community empowerment. Robert Putnam (2000) formulates social capital by referring to the characteristics of social organization, such as networks, norms, and beliefs that facilitate the coordination of cooperation for something whose benefits can be felt jointly. Social capital is so beneficial for individuals and organizations because the existence of social capital will provide benefits in the form of enabling people to solve common problems easily; facilitating community efforts to progress, social capital can foster solidarity, and social capital enables the achievement of common goals.

D. *Social Capital Measurement Methods*

Narayan and Cassidy (2001), there are various methods of measuring social capital that can be adapted to local conditions. These models are:

- *New South Wales Study*

Ony and Bullen (1997), developed a practical measurement tool to measure social capital on a community organization scale, and its impact on the development of public participation. This model uses 8 (eight) factors as indicators for social capital, namely: (a) participation at the local community level; (b) activities in a social context; (c) feelings of trust and security; (d) connections in the neighborhood; (e) connections with family and friends; (f) tolerance for differences; (g) life values; and (h) connections in the work environment.

- *The Barometer of Social Capital Colombia*

John Sudarsky (1999) developed a social capital measurement model using 8 (eight) dimensions, namely: (a) trust in institutions; (b) civic participation; (c) interdependence and reciprocity; (d) horizontal relations; (e) hierarchy; (f) social control; (g) civil administration; and (h) political participation.

- Integrated Questionnaire for The Measurement of Social Capital (SC-IQ)

This model was developed by Christiaan Grootaert, Deepa Narayan, Veronica Nyhan Jones, and Michael Woolcock (2004) with an emphasis on developing countries. This model aims to obtain quantitative data on various dimensions of social capital with the unit of analysis at the household level. In this model, 6 (six) indicators are used, namely: (a) work groups and networks; (b) trust and solidarity; (c) collective action and cooperation (cooperation); (d) information and communication; (e) social cohesion and inclusivity; and (f) empowerment and political action.

III. ANALYSIS METHOD

The research method used in this study is a quantitative research method. Quantitative research method is a form of research method that is used to examine certain populations or samples. Data collection uses research instruments. Data analysis is quantitative/statistical in nature, with the aim of testing established hypotheses. The data used in this study are primary data obtained through questionnaires and field observations and secondary data obtained through print media, literature review, and institutional data to determine community characteristics, conditions of social capital, and forms of community participation in the housing complex. Determination of the sample is done by using probability sampling technique, namely proportionate stratified random sampling. This sampling method was chosen because Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo has stratified characteristics as indicated by the types of houses, namely types 21, 36, and 45. The sample size in this study will be measured by the formula from Notoadmodjo (2003) namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{Nd^2 + 1}$$

Information:

n : Number of samples

N : Total population (2102 households)

d : Degree of accuracy (10%)

Based on this equation, a sample of 96 samples was obtained as presented in Table 1. Sampling was selected based on the type of house, this refers to Law No. 11 of 2011 where subsidy assistance is given for the maximum MBR type 36 and type 45 is non-subsidized. So, types 21 and 36 are required to do self-help and empower their environment, so it is interesting to study whether there are differences between types 21, 36 and 45 in participating. And the sample is divided equally between the existing house types, this is in accordance with the basic assumptions that must be met in the analysis, which will be more accurate to use for the same sample in each group (Sugiono, 2012).

TABLE I. Distribution of Questionnaire Distribution

House Type	Amount	Sample Totals
Type 21	418	32
Type 36	1535	32
Type 45	111	32
Shop	29	-
Total	2102	96

Data analysis was performed from questionnaire data processed through descriptive statistical analysis, weighting and regression analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to complement and describe the results of analysis of statistical data. The most frequently used data for this analysis technique is data in the form of images, tables and diagrams. Weighting analysis is used to determine the condition of social capital and the level of community participation. At the social capital level, 6 variables with 3 indicators are used, classified into 3 weighting categories based on low, medium, and high social capital. Where:

Score 576 - 1.344: Low social capital

Score 1.345 - 2.112: Moderate social capital

Score 2.113 - 2.880: High social capital

Meanwhile, in the community classification classification, 7 variables are used which are classified into 3 weighting categories based on low, medium, and high participation.

Where:

Score 224 - 522 : Low participation rate

Score 523 - 822 : Moderate level of participation

Score 823 - 1.120 : High participation rate

While the regression analysis will be used to determine the effect and degree of closeness of the relationship between community characteristics and social capital with forms of community participation. The form of the results of the linear regression analysis is the regression equation, which is a formula that looks for the value of the dependent variable from a known independent value (Santoso, 2016). The following are the results of the mathematical equations of linear regression analysis.

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_nX_n$$

Information:

Y : Dependent variable

a : Constant (number to be searched)

$b_1, b_2, b_3 \dots b_n$: Regression coefficient (number to be searched)

$X_1, X_2, X_3 \dots X_n$: Independent variable

The dependent variable chosen is community participation (Y). The independent variables selected in this analysis are community characteristics with the variables age (X_1), education level (X_2), type of work (X_3), income level (X_4), length of stay (X_5), residential status (X_6) and social capital variables. with group and network variables (X_7), trust and solidarity (X_8), collective action and cooperation (X_9), information and communication (X_{10}), social cohesion and inclusivity (X_{11}), and political empowerment and action (X_{12}).

The data analysis technique to answer the first question is to know the characteristics of the public housing type by using descriptive statistical analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis can provide an overview of the information in the table presented. The second question in this study is to determine the condition of the social capital of the Perumnas community using descriptive statistical analysis and weighting. The third question in the research is knowing the form of community participation using descriptive statistical analysis and weighting. The fourth question is knowing the effect of community characteristics and social capital on forms of community participation using multiple regression analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. *The characteristic type of society*

- Age has a positive effect in the form of participation, because the productive age between 31-45 years and 46-60 years has an influence on realizing types of activities that require assistance in the form of human labor to solve existing problems and of course get even more optimal results.
- Education provides direction and movement towards a person's behavior in carrying out social interactions with the surrounding environment. The still high percentage of people with high school graduation indicates that they do not yet have a good skills certificate.
- Community work influences a person's busyness to continue to earn income so that he can meet his needs. So that it has an impact on participation, because if residents who have been preoccupied with daily activities are less interested in attending meetings, discussions and seminars.
- Community income can affect participation in their environment, where people with higher incomes will also have a high ability and willingness to participate.
- The length of stay of a person in the environment influences people to work together and be involved in joint activities held in the environment where they live. This arises because of a feeling of shared destiny and responsibility because they live in the same area.
- Ownership of building status will affect the community in maintaining their residence and affect participation in joint activities to improve the surrounding environment.

B. *Conditions of Community Social Capital Existing*

Social capital is still in the bonding stage (as a binder), not yet as a bridge (bridging) that connects all potential citizens. This is marked by the groups that form the majority based on equality either because of kinship, ethnic equality, religious equality, economic equality, and have strong ties due to the intense meetings of its members, limited collaboration in the existing community, and funding within the group. These are generally self-supporting from their own contributions.

TABLE II. Community Social Capital Level

Variable	Indicator Statement	Type 21	Type 36	Type 45
Group & Networks	KJ1	304 (medium)	371 (high)	252 (medium)
	KJ2			
	KJ3			
Trust & Solidarity	KS1	381 (high)	428 (high)	343 (medium)
	KS2			
	KS3			
Collective action & Cooperation	AK1	279 (medium)	397 (medium)	267 (medium)
	AK2			
	AK3			
Information & Communication	IK1	331 (medium)	454 (high)	309 (medium)
	IK2			
	IK3			
Social Cohesion & Inclusivity	KI1	369 (high)	432 (high)	282 (medium)
	KI2			
	KI3			
Empowerment & Political Action	PT1	182 (low)	320 (medium)	244 (medium)
	PT2			
	PT3			
Total		1846 (medium)	2402 (high)	1697 (medium)

Based on these data, it can be concluded that there is a real difference, where the social capital of the type 36 resident communities is "higher" than the social capital of the type 21 and type 45 resident communities.

C. Forms of Community Participation

TABLE III. Forms of Involvement in Meetings

No	Form of Involvement	Type 21	Type 36	Type 45
1	Non participation	16	25	28
2	Giving proposal	10	2	-
3	Giving criticism	-	-	-
4	Giving suggestions	6	5	4

Although the number of respondents who were not active in meetings in the three types of dwellings was quite large, type 21 and type 36 had people who were quite active in meetings compared to type 45.

TABLE IV. Forms of Involvement in Implementation

No	Form of Involvement	Type 21	Type 36	Type 45
1	Donate property	9	11	23
2	Donate ideas	5	7	5
3	Donate energy	18	12	4
4	Donate expertise	-	2	-

From the table above, it can be seen that basically the respondents did not mind participating in joint activities. In other words, the level of participation of respondents is actually still quite high, only the manifestations have changed. Because many respondents are busy working, they generally prefer to protect money or facilities to support joint activities.

Fig 1. Level Of Public Participation of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo

Based on the figure, it can be interpreted that there is a real difference, where the participation of the type 36 resident communities is "higher" than the participation of the type 21 and type 45 resident communities.

D. The Influence of Community Characteristics and Social Capital on Forms of Community Participation

For the participation of the people of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo, the regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = -2.249 + 0.196X_1 + 0.182X_2 + 0.243X_3 + 0.174X_4 + 0.168X_5 + 0.060X_6 + 0.145X_7 + 0.239X_8 + 0.101X_9 + 0.353X_{10} + 0.222X_{11} + 0.089X_{12}$$

Information:

- Y : Community Participation
- X₁ : Age
- X₂ : Education Level
- X₃ : Type of work
- X₄ : Income Level
- X₅ : Length of stay
- X₆ : Occupancy Status

- X₇ : Working Groups and Networks
- X₈ : Trust and Solidarity
- X₉ : Collective Action and Cooperation
- X₁₀ : Information and Communication
- X₁₁ : Social Cohesion and Inclusivity
- X₁₂ : Empowerment and Political Action

The characteristics of the community and social capital have a significant effect on community participation in the management of Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo infrastructure facilities. When viewed from the regression coefficient, the variables that have the highest influence and level of closeness are information and communication variables (0.353), type of work (0.243), trust and solidarity (0.239) and cohesion and inclusivity (0.222). 3 of the 4 highest variables are variables of social capital, so it can be said that the increase in social capital has an effect on increasing the participation of the Perumnas Bukit Sendangmulyo community. When viewed in outline, the influence of characteristics and social capital on forms of community participation can be seen in the following table.

TABLE V. Community Characteristics, Social Capital And Community Participation

Variable	Type 21	Type 36	Type 45
Age	46-60 Year	31-45 Year	46-60 Year
Education Level	High school	High school	Collage
Type of work	trader	Private employees	Government employees
Income Level	IDR 1.600.000 - IDR 2.500.000	IDR 1.600.000 - IDR 2.500.000	IDR 2.500.000 - IDR 5.000.000
Length of stay	11-15 Year	>15 Year	5-10 Year
Social Capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective action & Cooperation • Social Cohesion & Inclusivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group & Networks • Trust & Solidarity • Information & Communication • Social Cohesion & Inclusivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust & Solidarity • Information & Communication
Level of participation	Medium	High	Low
Form of participation	Proposal Suggestions	Suggestions	Suggestions
	Energy	Property Energy	Property

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

In general, community participation for type 36 residents was higher than community participation for types 21 and 45 residents. This can be seen from the large amount of participation provided by the community. Most of the participation was given by residents of type 21 are suggestions, suggestions and energy, to residents of type 36 are suggestions, property and labor, while residents of type 45 are suggestions and property.

Forms of community participation are proposals, suggestions and energy for type 21 residents are influenced by the age group 46-60 years (older) who have more feelings of affection and pay attention to housing environmental problems. The majority of high school graduates who work as traders believe that participation must be carried out because they respect the rules so they need to be obeyed, but in participating they are in the form of labor because judging from their low income, IDR 1,600,000 - IDR 2,500,000. living for 11-15 years makes the community have participation classified as "moderate" due to quite a long experience in society so that it also affects social capital (classified as "moderate") from the aspects of groups and work networks and social cohesion and inclusivity.

The form of community participation in type 36 residents are advice, property, and labor, this is influenced by the age group 31-45 years on the basis of the dominant element of rationality in participating. The majority of high school graduates who work as private employees believe that participation must be carried out because they respect the rules so they need to be obeyed, don't ask too many questions, and do what they are told. They participate in the form of property and labor because if seen from their income, even though it is low, namely IDR 1,600,000 - IDR 2,500,000, besides labor they also continue to provide a savings contribution that is used to visit people, death, and cleaning. Living for > 15 years makes them care about other people, such as helping each other and being able to work together which has an impact on the level of participation classified as "high". This is also due to social capital (classified as "high") that exists in society from the aspects of groups and networks, trust and solidarity, information and communication, and social cohesion and inclusivity.

The form of community participation for residents of type 45 is in the form of advice and property, this is influenced by the age group of 46-60 years (older) who have more feelings of affection and pay attention to environmental problems. Perumnas believes that participation is a social action because of his quality or achievements. As a college graduate. They participate in the form of property because they are busy as civil servants and earn IDR 2,500,000 - IDR 5,000,000 believing that participating in the form of property makes it easier for them to participate. Living in Perumnas for 5-10 years has not made the community have strong and familiar bonds where they live so that it affects "medium" participation. This is also due to social capital (classified as

"medium") that exists in society from the aspects of trust and solidarity and information and communication.

B. Recommendation

In accordance with the condition of the quality of the residential environment that is decreasing with the behavior of people who do not care about problems caused by a lack of community participation, it is necessary to increase the potential possessed according to the characteristics of the community to be able to increase public awareness about solving problems that occur. Socialization regarding the forms of problems that occur and the impact that will occur due to the decline in environmental quality in future survival, forms a forum for increasing community capacity and strengthening institutions/organizations or religious forums. There are policies/guidelines regarding processes and methods for environmental improvement, community involvement to participate from the planning stage to post-implementation. In addition, the policy is also adapted to the conditions and characteristics of the local community.

To test further about the effect of forms of community participation by taking into account the characteristics of society and social capital, a similar study or research is needed with different community characteristics in other areas in Semarang City, so that this concept can be used as a model to improve housing environments in urban areas due to the decline in environmental quality, an appropriate program can be developed to accelerate the improvement of environmental quality in the city of Semarang.

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